

Factors Affecting Career Choice in the Field of Nursing Practice Among Selected Graduates of Perpetual College of Manila Batch 2018-2024

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Abstract

The study factors affecting career choice in the field of nursing practice among selected graduates of Perpetual Help College of Manila Batch 2018–2024 explores the internal and external influences that shape the career decisions of nursing graduates. It gives emphasis on how personal attributes such as skills and abilities, values and beliefs, past experiences, emotions, and anxiety and stress interact with external conditions like financial benefits, family influence, work environment, school influence and professors or teachers to guide graduates in choosing their field of practice. The study also emphasizes the importance of early clinical exposure, career counseling, and diverse training experiences in helping graduates develop self-

awareness and make informed, confident career choices within the healthcare sector.

This study examined the internal and external factors influencing field-of-practice selection among registered nursing graduates of Perpetual Help College of Manila (PHCM), Batch 2018–2024. Guided by Holland’s Theory of Career Choice, King’s Goal Attainment Theory, and Benner’s Novice-to-Expert Theory, the study explored how personal competencies, values, and environmental influences shape early-career decisions. A quantitative descriptive design was employed using a validated questionnaire administered to 54 purposively selected graduates. Data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, and weighted mean. Results showed

that internal factors, particularly skills and abilities ($\bar{x} = 4.54$), values/beliefs ($\bar{x} = 4.44$), and past experiences ($\bar{x} = 4.26$), strongly influenced career choices. Among external factors, financial benefits ($\bar{x} = 4.40$), family influence ($\bar{x} = 4.20$), and work environment ($\bar{x} = 4.18$) were the most significant. Graduates predominantly worked in private hospitals and specialized units such as wards, operating rooms, and emergency departments. The findings suggest that career choices are multifactorial and evolve through early professional exposure. Implications for

nursing education, hospital administration, and career development programs are discussed. The study findings reveal that PHCM nursing graduates rely on a combination of internal and external factors when choosing their field of practice. Internal factors, particularly skills and abilities, play a significant role in shaping field-of-practice choices, demonstrating the importance of personal competency alignment. This supports Benner's Novice-to-Expert Theory, which identifies skill development as a core component of professional growth (Wei et al., 2021).

Keywords: *Field of Practice, Career Choice, Nursing Graduates, Internal Factors, External Factors*

INTRODUCTION

The nursing profession is integral to healthcare delivery, yet many nursing graduates struggle to identify a field of practice that aligns with their competencies, values, and long-term career aspirations. Career choices in nursing are shaped by a combination of internal factors such as personal values, emotions, and self-efficacy, and external influences including family expectations, educational support, financial considerations, and workplace conditions (Sharif et al., 2019; Kandil et al., 2020). Misalignment between these factors and actual work conditions contributes to professional dissatisfaction, unclear identity formation, and early turnover.

Holland's Theory of Career Choice posits that individuals experience greater satisfaction when their personality traits and competencies align with their occupational environment (Holland, 2019). In nursing, this alignment is critical, as nurses who perceive a strong fit between their skills and their practice area demonstrate higher retention and professional growth. Similarly, King's Goal Attainment Theory highlights the importance of interpersonal interactions in achieving career goals, while Benner's Novice-to-Expert Theory highlights how nurses develop competence through experience and reflection, underscoring the role of past clinical exposures in shaping career preferences (Wei et al., 2021).

Globally, newly licensed nurses frequently leave their first workplaces due to limited support and unclear career pathways (Ejebu et al., 2023). Studies in Asia show that career self-efficacy and self-leadership are essential for stabilizing career identity among nursing students (Kim & Ko, 2020; Kim, 2019). In the Philippines, intrinsic motivators such as meaningful work and opportunities for growth have been found to influence career choices more strongly than financial factors (Fontanilla et al., 2023). Despite this, there remains limited research examining how internal and external factors simultaneously influence field-of-practice choices among newly registered nurses, particularly within specific institutional contexts.

This study addresses this gap by examining the internal and external determinants of field-of-practice selection among nursing graduates from Perpetual Help College of Manila (PHCM), Batch 2018–2024. Guided by Holland's, King's, and Benner's theoretical frameworks, the study aims to generate insights that can strengthen career guidance programs, workplace integration strategies, and retention initiatives in nursing education and healthcare institutions.

Theoretical Framework

In the process of achieving goals and careers, nurses face a lot of challenges which include factors such as internal, external and interpersonal. In internal factors, it includes the decisions or choices an individual opted for, satisfaction, motivation, attitude and skills. External factors on the other hand include influence from family, teacher and environment. Additionally, interpersonal factors include influence from peers, colleagues, classmates and others.

According to Gonzalo (2024), the Theory of Imogen King, "The Goal Attainment Theory" states that a process of action, reaction and interaction by which an individual shares their perception in every situation where each perceives the other and the situation. Through communication, they set goals, explore, and agree on means to achieve goals. This theory explains how an individual acts, reacts and interacts with others to set goals and obtain their career in the future.

Furthermore, the study focuses on the process to guide and direct nurses in the nurse patient relationship going hand in hand with their patient to meet good health goals which reciprocate to an individual's effort and goals in achieving their careers. An individual may work hand in hand during application with their employer to be able to set the goal needed in the institution.

Lastly, it has a great importance in the progress of this study for it provides a framework that will serve as a guide throughout the process of research. It provides a clear understanding of how growth and development helps continue and change an individual's behavioral levels of activities. The processes that take place in the life of every individual help them achieve their potential capacity for achieving desired goals and self-actualization.

According to Wayne (2024), Patricia Benner's Novice to Expert Theory mainly concentrated on nursing and professional growth describing the gradual acquisition of skills and knowledge by nurses. In terms of skill acquisition, it is believed that an individual tends to acquire competences that can affect their employment choices as they advance from novice to expert stages. Knowing where they shine can aid their choices on what career to pursue. The significance of experiential learning emphasized by Benner's theory is a person's desire to acquire specific experiences that will help them develop their talents that may give an impact on their career choices.

Also, the theory states that having mentors can help an individual grow in any field. The need of receiving career coaching from more experienced colleagues is emphasized by Benner's concept. The emphasis on experience reflection can assist people in identifying their strengths and shortcomings which can impact their career decisions as they look for positions that complement their skill set. As an individual moves through Benner's stages, they may find their interests and ambitions change which leads to transformations in job pathways based on acquired expertise, abilities and confidence.

This can help individuals understand their development within a career leading to informed choices about their professional paths which is important in achieving excellent career choices. This theory has a great connection in our study because the theory gives emphasis on the different steps and paths an individual might experience and overcome in making an informed career choice.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure I. Conceptual Framework

Based on the conceptual framework, there are different factors affecting career choices in the field of practice of an individual. These are the external and internal factors which have a great impact on an individual’s field of practice and career.

The first box describes the external factors which include family, environment, financial, institution and teachers that comprises the factors affecting the individuals’ career choice. This factor has great importance and provides influences on the career choices of every individual.

On the other hand, the second box represents internal factors including anxiety, decision, emotions, perception, skills, beliefs, experiences and attitude. This factor comprises the inner thoughts of an individual in achieving career and field of practice.

These factors can greatly influence an individual choice of career, decision and field of practice as they go through stages of career growth and development. This may also hinder an individual’s career growth and practices, thus providing programs that will help in their chosen field of practice would be a great help in order for them to achieve their career success.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine factors that affect the career choice in the field of practice among nursing graduates of Perpetual College of Manila Batch 2018-2024. It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents be described in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age

- 1.2 Gender
- 1.3 Year of Graduation
- 1.4 Nature of Work
- 1.5 Department/Area of Work
- 1.6 Length of Service
2. Which of the following internal factors that affect the career choice in the field of practice of nursing graduates in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. Skills and Abilities
 - 2.2 Values and Beliefs
 - 2.3 Past Experiences
 - 2.4 Emotion
 - 2.5 Anxiety/Stress
3. Which of the following external factors that affect the career choice in the field of practice of nursing graduates in terms of the following:
 - 3.1 Financial Benefits
 - 3.2 Family Influence
 - 3.3 Work Environment
 - 3.4 School Influence
 - 3.5 Professors/ Teachers
4. Based on the findings, what recommendation can be made to the nursing students in order to enhance self-awareness in career choice in the field of practice?

Literature Review

Individuals prefer careers that allow them to be around like-minded individuals, use their skills, express their values, and take on enjoyable roles, with behavior being influenced by personality and environment. In a literature by John Holland (2019), "Theory of Career Choice" believed that individuals prefer a comfortable career in terms of having similar preferences and in a setting which they will be able to perform to the best of their abilities

In an article by Kim and Ko (2020) entitled, "Relationship between Self-Leadership, Career Decision making Self-Efficacy and Career Identity of Nursing Students", it's descriptive research to analyze why the turnover rate of nurses in Korea suddenly spiked from only 13.8% in 2018 to 42.7% within one year. One of the reasons that was suggested is maladaptation of nurses, hence it was shown that some nurses choose nursing without identity for a career identity, hence leading to a shift of plans of preferring other jobs due to not adapting to the clinical field. Because of this, a study was conducted in order to reduce the turnover rate of nurses and establish a clear career identity among the respondents, especially when in a state of student nurses, meaning in college level, establishing a career identity is the most crucial towards a career success with the proper career decision-making.

Occupational choices always happen to an individual, particularly students entering college. Because of the diverse choices for a program, it often leads to difficulties for students in terms of choosing their desired future careers. An article by Sharif et al. (2019) "Factors Influencing Career Choices" aimed to explore factors such as mothers, fathers, tutors, future income, future status, and societal difference on how they affect career choices for students entering collegiate level. A cross-sectional data that was based on a primary data collection was acquired from different students from universities based in Karachi via developed questionnaires and through non-probabilistic convenience sampling. In conclusion, this study provides a comparative analysis on various factors on what shapes a student in choosing their career choice.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A descriptive quantitative research design was used to examine the internal and external factors affecting career choice in the field-of-practice selection among nursing graduates of Perpetual Help College of Manila (PHCM), Batch 2018–2024. This design was chosen because it allows systematic measurement of perceptions, attitudes, and factors that shape career decisions.

Data will be collected for the study using a total enumeration approach where graduate registered nurses will be given a Likert scale type of questionnaires to collect information about their chosen field of practice and the significance of different factors which includes internal and external factors .

Before the data collection, the researchers prepared a letter that sought approval from the Dean of the College of Nursing as well as the registrar of the school to identify the possible respondents of the study.

After seeking approval from the concerned department, the researchers prepared questionnaires for pilot testing that will be administered to 10 respondents to assess if the answers are relevant to the data needed in the study.

Data gathering is planned to commence for 2 weeks up to the collation of data collected. After the collation of data, it will be subject for analysis to draw conclusions and create findings of the study. The whole duration of the study is expected to last for a month until findings and conclusions are drawn.

Respondents

The target population consisted of 202 nursing graduates from Batch 2018–2024. Out of this population, 54 respondents met the inclusion criteria and agreed to participate. Purposive sampling was used because it is appropriate for identifying participants who possess specific characteristics or experiences relevant to the research objectives

The respondents include registered nurse (RN) who graduated from PHCM between 2018 and 2024 and currently practicing in any nursing-related field in both public and private hospitals working locally and abroad.

Exclusion criteria includes those nursing graduates not practicing as Nurse and do not belong to batch 2018 - 2024.

Instruments of the Study

Data were gathered using a structured researcher-developed questionnaire, created based on instruments used in prior studies on nursing career decision-making.

The questionnaire consisted of three major sections:

- Demographic Profile
Includes age, gender, year of graduation, workplace type, department/unit, length of service, and nature of work.
- Internal Factors
Items assessed personal beliefs, values, skills, past experiences, emotions, and stress/anxiety influencing career choices.
- External Factors
Items measured the perceived influence of family, school/academic experiences, professors/mentors, financial considerations, and workplace environment.

Internal and external factor items were rated using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree), a widely accepted approach for quantifying subjective perceptions. To enrich the quantitative data, brief follow-up interviews were conducted with selected respondents to gather additional contextual insights.

The questionnaire underwent content validation by three experts in nursing education and research, who evaluated each item for clarity, relevance, and alignment with study objectives. Revisions were implemented based on their feedback. Reliability testing yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.808, indicating high internal consistency and suitability for research use.

Data Collection

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Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. Frequency and percentage were used for demographic variables. Weighted mean and overall mean for internal and external factors. These statistical treatments helped identify patterns and the relative influence of each factor on career choice in the field-of-practice decisions. Results were presented in tables to improve clarity and facilitate interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations Ethics is critical in research because it protects participants and guarantees that the study is conducted responsibly. According to Flick (2018) and Israel & Hay (2020), ethical practices promote trust, transparency, and the integrity of the research process. To accomplish this, the researchers explicitly explain the goal of the study and ensure that participants understand their role. This responsibility is guided by three essential ethical ideas. Anonymity preserves participants' identity while encouraging honest responses. Confidentiality protects personal information and respects participant privacy. Informed consent enables respondents to fully understand the study before consenting to participate, encouraging transparency and confidence. Finally, voluntary participation ensures that individuals can join or quit the research at any time without incurring unfavorable consequences.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive quantitative research design was used to examine the internal and external factors that affect career choice in the field-of-practice selection among nursing graduates of Perpetual Help College of Manila (PHCM), Batch 2018–2024. This design was chosen because it allows systematic measurement of perceptions, attitudes, and factors that shape career decisions.

A total enumeration approach was initially planned to invite all graduates from the identified batches. However, purposive sampling was ultimately applied to include only individuals who: 1) were registered nurses, and 2) were currently employed in a nursing-related field. This sampling strategy ensured that only respondents with relevant career experience contributed data to the study.

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used because it is appropriate for identifying participants who possess specific characteristics or experiences relevant to the research objectives. The respondents include registered nurse (RN) who graduated from PHCM between 2018 and 2024 and currently practicing in any nursing-related field in both public and private hospitals working locally and abroad. Exclusion criteria includes those nursing graduates not practicing as Nurse and do not belong to batch 2018 - 2024.

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Ethical approval was secured from the Dean of the College of Nursing, and participants provided informed consent prior to participation. The questionnaire was administered in both online formats (via email, Messenger, Viber) and face-to-face sessions to maximize accessibility and encourage participation. Responses were anonymized and stored securely to maintain confidentiality.

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. Frequency and percentage were used for demographic variables. Weighted mean and overall mean for internal and external factors. These statistical treatments helped identify patterns and the relative influence of each factor on career choice in the field-of-practice decisions. Results were presented in tables to improve clarity and facilitate interpretation.

RESULTS

This study investigated the demographic profiles which includes age, gender, year of graduation, nature of work, department/area of work, length of service, internal and external factors that affect the career choice in the field-of-practice selection among nursing graduates of Perpetual Help College of Manila (PHCM), Batch 2018–2024. Data from 54 respondents were analyzed and presented according to demographic characteristics, internal factors, and external factors.

PART 1: Demographic Data

This part is composed of different tables for specific demographic profile variables of the study. It consists of six tables, Table 1.1 to 1.6, with the essential information about the respondents' age, gender, year of graduation, type of institution, field of practice, and length of practice. These were utilized to determine the demographic profile of each respondent.

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile in terms of Age (in years)

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
23-27	32	59.26%
28-33	15	27.78%
34-38	4	7.41%
39-43	3	5.55%
TOTAL	54	100%

In terms of age, The data suggested that the majority of respondents are in their mid-20s to late 20s with a few older individuals contributing to the sample. The respondents were primarily young adults, with 59.26% aged 23–27 years and 27.78% aged 28–33 years. Only a small proportion belonged to older age groups (34–38 years: 7.41%; 39–43 years: 5.55%). This distribution indicates that most participants are early-career nurses actively exploring and consolidating their professional identities.

1.2 Demographic Data of the Respondents in terms of Gender

GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
MALE	16	29.63%
FEMALE	38	70.37%
TOTAL	54	100%

This indicates that the sample has a higher proportion of female respondents than male respondents. A majority (70.37%) were female, reflecting the global gender trend in nursing (Fontanilla et al., 2023; Kandil et al., 2020). Most respondents graduated between 2019 and 2023, suggesting relatively recent entry into professional practice.

1.3 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Year of Graduation

YEAR	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
2018	7	12.96%
2019	14	25.94%
2020	5	9.26%
2021	8	14.81%
2022	8	14.81%
2023	8	14.81%
2024	4	7.41%
TOTAL	54	100%

In terms of year of graduation, it is evident that the majority of the respondents graduated in 2019 with 25.94%. An equal number of respondents graduated in 2021, 2022, and 2023 with 14.81% each year. A smaller percentage graduated in 2018 with 12.96%. However, the year with the fewest respondents is

2020 with 9.26% and 2024 with only 7.41%. In total, there are 54 respondents and the data covers PHCM nursing graduates from the years 2018 to 2024. Overall, the data showed a fairly even distribution of respondents from 2019 to 2024.

1.4 Demographic of the Respondents in terms type of Institution

NATURE OF WORK	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Private OPD Clinic	2	3.7%
Private Hospital	38	70.37%
Public Hospital	13	24.07%
Homecare	1	1.86%
TOTAL	54	100%

In terms of employment settings, the majority (70.37%) were employed in private hospitals, followed by public hospitals (24.07%), outpatient clinics (3.7%), and homecare (1.86%). This aligns with literature stating that career decisions are shaped by job availability, salary, benefits, and perceived opportunities for growth (Ejebu et al., 2023; Wei et al., 2021).

1.5 Demographic Data of the Respondents in terms of Field of Practice

DEPARTMENT/ AREA OF WORK	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Ward	11	20.37%
ICU	5	9.26%
Homecare	1	1.85%
High Intensity	1	1.85%
Neurology	1	1.85%
OPD	6	11.11%
DR	4	7.41%
ER	8	14.81%
Cardiology	3	5.56%
Hemodialysis	4	7.41%
OR	10	18.52%
TOTAL	54	100%

Respondents were distributed across multiple healthcare departments, with notable representation in Wards (20.37%), Operating Rooms (18.52%), and Emergency Rooms (14.81%). Other specialties included Outpatient Departments (11.11%), Hemodialysis (7.41%), and critical care units. This diversity illustrates varied clinical interests and opportunities presented within the local healthcare system (Holland, 2019; Kim, 2019).

1.6 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency	Percentage
6 years	1	1.85%
5 years	9	16.67%
4 years	4	7.41%
3 ½ years	1	1.85%
3 years	10	18.52%
2 years	12	22.22%
1 years and 8 months	1	1.85%
1 ½ year	1	1.85%
1 years	7	12.96%
8 months	4	7.41%
7 months	4	7.41%
TOTAL	54	100%

Table 1.6 shows the distribution of respondents according to their length of service. Most respondents had 2–5 years of clinical experience, indicating that many are still navigating career exploration and professional development periods commonly associated with re-evaluation of career goals and workplace fit.

Internal Factors Affecting Field of Practice

This table consists of only one table, which is the variable of internal factors affecting the field of practice. These were used to describe the internal factors affecting the field of practice.

Table 2. Internal Factors Affecting the Field of Practice

Internal Factor	Mean	Verbal Indicator
Skills & Abilities	4.54	Strongly Agree
Values & Beliefs	4.44	Agree
Past Experience	4.26	Agree
Emotion	4.10	Agree
Anxiety / Stress	3.36	Agree
Overall Mean	4.34	Agree

Legend: 4.5-5.0 - Strongly Agree 3.5 - 4.49 - Agree 2.5 - 3.49 - Neutral 1.5 - 2.49 - Disagree
 1.0 - 1.49 - Strongly Disagree

Table 2 includes internal factors such as personal values, skills, emotions, anxiety, and past experiences. Skills and abilities had the highest mean score, followed by values and beliefs, past experiences, emotions, and anxiety/stress. The overall mean of 4.34 suggests that internal factors strongly influence field-of-practice decisions.

These findings reinforce the notion that career decisions among early-career nurses are shaped by self-efficacy, competence, and personal values (Kim & Ko, 2020; Sharif et al., 2019). The prominence of skills and abilities suggests that graduates tend to select practice areas that match their perceived strengths, consistent with Holland's Theory of Career Choice, which posits that person-environment fit drives satisfaction and retention (Holland, 2019).

External Factors Affecting Field of Practice

This table consists of only one table, which is the variable of external factors affecting the field of practice. These were used to describe the external factors affecting the field of practice.

Table 3. External Factors Affecting the Field of Practice

External Factor	Mean	Verbal Indicator
Financial Benefits	4.40	Agree
Family Influence	4.20	Agree
Work Environment	4.18	Agree
School Influence	4.00	Agree
Professors/Teachers	3.68	Agree
Total Weighted Mean	4.09	Agree

Legend: 4.5-5.0 - Strongly Agree 3.5 - 4.49 - Agree 2.5 - 3.49 - Neutral 1.5 - 2.49 - Disagree
1.0 - 1.49 - Strongly Disagree

External factors included family influence, school influence, financial considerations, professors/mentors, and work environment. Financial benefits scored the highest, followed by family influence, and work environment. School influence and professors/teachers were considered less impactful. The overall mean was 4.09, indicating that external factors moderately influenced career decisions (Table 3).

These findings are consistent with studies highlighting the centrality of financial needs, family encouragement, and workplace conditions in shaping early-career nurses' decisions (Potira et al., 2019; Wei et al., 2021). The relatively lower influence of school and professors suggests that once nurses enter the workforce, practical and economic considerations overshadow academic influences.

DISCUSSION

Analysis

The demographic distribution suggests that many PHCM graduates are still navigating early career transitions. The diverse distribution across clinical areas underscores how opportunities, personal strengths, and early workplace experiences influence the direction of their careers.

These findings collectively highlight that career decision-making is multifactorial, aligning with contemporary career development models that emphasize the interplay of personal identity, environmental influences, and experiential learning.

The study reveals that PHCM nursing graduates rely on a combination of internal and external factors when choosing their field of practice. Internal factors, particularly skills and abilities, play a significant role in shaping field-of-practice choices, demonstrating the importance of personal competency

alignment. This supports Benner's Novice-to-Expert Theory, which identifies skill development as a core component of professional growth (Wei et al., 2021).

External factors, especially financial benefits and family influence, also significantly shape decision-making. This highlights the reality that early-career professionals often consider economic stability and the expectations of significant others when selecting a clinical specialty.

The strong influence of the work environment reflects the importance of supportive, safe, and growth-oriented workplaces, a factor repeatedly identified as essential for retention.

Providing career counseling programs in universities and hospitals can help graduates develop self-concept and informed decision-making regarding their field of practice. Early exposure to diverse practice areas and mentorship may enhance professional growth and career satisfaction among nursing graduates.

Conclusions

Nursing graduates from PHCM Batch 2018–2024 are primarily in the early stages of their careers, with most having 2–5 years of professional experience. Their career decisions are shaped by both internal attributes such as skills, beliefs, emotions, and prior experiences and external conditions such as financial incentives, family influence, and workplace environment. These findings echo Kim and Ko's (2020) research, which highlights the importance of self-leadership and career decision-making self-efficacy in forming a strong career identity among nursing students.

Similarly, Mann-Isah, Ameen, and Jassim (2019) emphasize that external motivators, particularly financial considerations and familial expectations, significantly impact medical students' career preferences. Skills and abilities emerged as the strongest internal determinant, while financial benefits and family influence were the strongest external determinants. These results affirm that field-of-practice choices are driven by a combination of personal competency alignment and practical contextual needs. The preference for private-sector employment and varied clinical specialties suggests that career trajectories are diverse and influenced by available opportunities, professional growth potential, and early clinical exposure.

In order to enhance self awareness in career choice in the field of practice among nursing graduates of Perpetual Help College of Manila the following recommendations were made. First, exposing nursing students during on the job training to the different fields in healthcare can develop their skills and allow them to explore and be prepared in embracing their future career. Second, the nursing graduates must invest time in discovering and learning the different fields in health care that will enhance their professional identity and professional growth. Third, By providing career counseling programs in universities and hospitals in order to develop self-concept and informed decision-making regarding their career choice in the field of practice. Lastly, encourage graduates to gain experience in various healthcare environments to find out their strengths and interests that can contribute to being more informed and build confidence in their practice.

Recommendations

In order to enhance self awareness in career choice in the field of practice among nursing graduates of Perpetual Help College of Manila the following recommendations were made:

- Exposing nursing students during on-the-job training to the different fields in healthcare can develop their skills and allow them to explore and be prepared in embracing their future career.
- The nursing graduates must invest time in discovering and learning the different fields in health care that will enhance their professional identity and professional growth.
- Provide career counseling programs in universities and hospitals to develop self-concept and informed decision-making regarding their career choice in the field of practice.

- To gain experience in various healthcare environments to find out their strengths and interests that can contribute to being more informed and build confidence in their practice.

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